

Watermarking Biometric System for Human Ownership Identification

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Abstract

Biometric Watermarking Scheme was proposed with the view of protecting, labelling and improving efficiency of Biometric Recognition System. The watermarking of the biometric image (fingerprint) was achieved through Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) Method. This is beneficial as the Watermarking Scheme for Ownership Biometric Trait Identification can be able to distinguish Biometric images through logo. The stored fingerprint (template fingerprint) should be unmarked before verification. Another important process that needs to be performed is image pre-processing. The biometric process later involved biometric trait image enhancement. Binarization, Histogram Equalization and removal of noise through median filtering are the biometric image enhancement that was done in this work. At authentication point, distinct features of captured fingerprint (Input Fingerprint) were extracted and matched with features from stored or template fingerprint. Finally, authentication result can be printed on a report for future use. The performance evaluation was achieved through Standard Performance Metric which are Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Square Error (MSE). True Positive Rate (TPR), False Positive Rate (FPR) and Precision. The highest PSNR for watermarked Ear, Face and Fingerprint are 37.81, 26.95, 30.81 respectively. The highest MSE for Watermarked Ear, Face and Fingerprint are 25.31, 322.81 and 61.39 respectively. The fingerprint Recognition was also evaluated through TPR = .0.88, FPR = 0.12 and Precision = 0.88.

Keywords: Watermarking, Authentication, Biometric, Enhancement, Fingerprint

INTRODUCTION

Watermarking Biometric System for Human Ownership Identification is the process of individual identification that involves labeling of biometric traits to form secret and easily differentiated data. The system can be achieved through extraction and protection of distinct features from biological traits that can be captured in form of images. In this study, the Watermarking scheme utilized fingerprints traits. It is very essential to control and prevent attackers to easily detect and perceive biometric traits which can be transmitted for strict monitoring of access to activities and properties (Authentication purpose). Prevention of fake messages from fraudsters and prevention of unauthorized access need to be achieved through biometric trait authentication (Vivek *et al.* , 2011)

This work is an improvement over existing Biometric System which is a process of using behavioral or biological trait for human identification. Biometric trait authentication is to verify an individual using biometric system like fingerprint Recognition, facial recognition. To improve the security of Biometric trait or Identification of individual, Kumar *et al.*, (2012) discussed steganography which is process of hiding existence of an image. Bartlow *et al.*, 2007., described watermarking as means of inserting a pattern of bits into a digital image, audio or video file that identifies the file's copyright information (author, right etc.)

Watermarking Scheme can also be applied to biometric system to differentiate and label fingerprint, facial image and other biometric trait for each school or organization. Watermarking can be visible or invisible (Tarar *et al.*, 2012). The watermarking in this biometric model is visible.

Watermarking Scheme for Ownership Biometric Trait Identification also entails fingerprint recognition where distinct features were extracted from captured fingerprint. The distinct features include fingerprint ridges and valley. Authentication or Verification of fingerprint were determined by matching distinct features from captured or input fingerprint with distinct features of template fingerprint. Yuliang *et al.*, 2003 explained that authentication of captured fingerprint that can be done by comparing and matching of minutiae or ridge features of input and template fingerprint. Protection of this distinct minutiae feature especially fingerprint image should also be taken into consideration. The existing biometric system does not take into consideration security and protection of biometric traits that are captured in form of image. It has been observed that there is probability that fingerprint captured for different school or organization will mix up, if watermarking scheme to label biometric image are not put into consideration. The aim of this work is to implement watermarking scheme for ownership biometric trait identification to protect stored biometric image (Fingerprint) that can be utilized to verify an individual during life check.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Classification of Watermarking Scheme

Watermarking can also be classified based on human perceptible as visible watermarking and invisible watermarking Tarar *et al.*, (2012). Information inserted through visible watermarking can be easily viewed on biometric image while watermarked biometric context of invisible watermark otherwise known as robust watermark which is equivalent to original image.

Classification of digital watermarking technique

A watermark can also be described as a signal added to digital data (audio, video and still images) that can be extracted later to make an insertion about the data.

Digital watermarking techniques can be classified into two

Robust Watermark: Robust watermark are designed to be hard to remove and to resist common image manipulation procedures. They are useful for copyright and ownership assertion purposes.

Fragile Watermark: Fragile watermarks (or authentication watermarks) are easily corrupted by any image-processing procedure. Watermarks for checking the image integrity can be fragile because if the watermark is removed, the watermark detection algorithm will correctly report the corruption of the image.

Mohit *et al.*, 2003 proposed LSB (Least Significant Bit) steganalysis of insertion method using discrete algorithm to hide secret information in a cover image. The basic purpose is to make communication unintelligible to those who do not possess right key to a cover image.

Itsu and Tu (2019) proposed digital watermarking to hide data and also for identification of information. Watermarking was described as mean of adding undetectable identifying marks such as author or copyright information into images without degrading its visual quality.

Philippe parra (2003) ceated an accurate program for fingerprint identification which was done using minutiae points based algorithm. The number of points for Template fingerprint (T) and Input fingerprint (I) were indicated as shown below.

$$T = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n\} \text{ with } m_i = \{x_i, y_i, \theta_i\} \quad i = 1 \dots M \quad (2.1)$$

$$T = \{m'_1, m'_2, \dots, m'_n\} \text{ with } m'_j = \{x'_j, y'_j, \theta'_j\} \quad j = 1 \dots n \quad (2.2)$$

Two minutiae points m_i and m'_j were considered to match, if their position and orientation are close which can be represented using spatial distance (sd) and direction difference (dd).

$$sd(m_i, m'_j) = \sqrt{(x_i - x'_j)^2 + (y_i - y'_j)^2} < R_0 \quad (2.3)$$

$$dd(m_i, m'_j) = \text{Min}(|\theta'_j - \theta_i|, 360 - |\theta'_j - \theta_i|) < \theta_0 \quad (2.9)$$

Where x_i and y_i are x and y co-ordinates for template fingerprint points

x'_j and y'_j are x and y co-ordinates for input fingerprint points

θ_i, θ'_j are direction of template and input fingerprint points respectively

Note: R_0 and θ_0 were thresholds used to identify that a point fits well, 30^0 and 20^0 were chosen respectively. Security measures like cryptography, steganography were not introduced as stipulated in the diagram above. There is need to add more feature vector like orientation.

Ankita *et al.* (2014) involved fingerprint image enhancement (binarization and thinning), feature extraction and subsequent minutiae matching. The distinct feature that were extracted are ridge endings and bifurcation from image by examining local neighbourhood of each ridge pixel using 3×3 window. The method for features extraction was crossing number (CN) method. CN was defined as half sum of differences between pairs of adjacent pixel.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section describes methodology adopted to achieve set of objectives. In this section, biometric image enhancements which are Binarization, Histogram equalization and median filtering for improving and removing noise from fingerprint images were discussed. Processes that were performed to watermark biometric images were also fully explained. Feature extractions and matching of distinct features from stored fingerprint were also revealed.

Biometric Image Enhancement

Image enhancement was done mainly to increase the fingerprint image quality and make it clearer. This made feature extraction to be done appropriately and accurately to get correct feature matching result. There is need for enhancement because accurate fingerprint image from scanners sometimes were not captured with perfect quality. The image enhancement was achieved through Histogram Equalization, Binarization and Noise removal.

Histogram Equalization

Histogram Equalization is to expand pixel value distribution of an image so as to increase perceptual information (Chandhary *et al.*, 2014). Histogram Equalization technique was applied to enhance and increase fingerprint image perception.

Binarization Process

Binarization improves contrast between ridges and valleys in a fingerprint image and consequently facilitates extraction of minutiae (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2012). Enhanced binarization was adopted to transform pixel value to 1, if value is greater than mean intensity value of image; otherwise, it was set to zero. To remove selected foreground pixels from binary images, thinning was used to eliminate redundant pixels of ridges till ridges are just one pixel wide.

Watermarking of Biometric Image

Watermarking can be achieved by inserting ownership logo to fingerprint to easily differentiate fingerprint image from other fingerprint that are utilized by other organisation. This is important since most schools and organisation now use fingerprint for attendance and authentication purpose. The watermarking of biometric image will be achieved through Discrete Cosine Transform. Determination of scaling factor will be initially done before insertion and extraction of watermark. This will be performed purposely to improve the efficiency of the watermarking process.

Determination of Scaling and Embedding Factor

It is very importance to determine scaling factor and embedding factor for efficient result.

To compute the scaling factor of the biometric image, the following must be initially determination

- 1) Mean of the biometric image
- 2) Mean of the Dc coefficient of logo or watermark image
- 3) Variance of the DC coefficient of host image
- 4) Variance of the Dc coefficient of logo or watermark image
- 5) V is the addition of first value of DC coefficient of host and watermark

$$V = I^h(0,0) + I^w(0,0) \quad (3.1)$$

Scaling factor of the biometric image can be computed using the defined parameters as written below.

$$\alpha_{bm} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2)}} \text{Exp} \frac{[V-(\mu_1+\mu_1)]^2}{2(\sigma_1^2+\sigma_2^2)} \quad (3.2)$$

The embedding factor (β_m) is subtraction of scaling factor from one. $\beta_m = 1 - \alpha_{bm}$

Insertion of Watermark

The watermarking is divided into insertion of watermark and extraction of watermark. The watermarking of the biometric images involves transforming the images to DCT domain. This means transforming from spatial domain to DCT domain. The next step is determination of scaling factor (γ) and embedding factor (β)

According to ying yang *et al*; 2010, the insertion of the watermark image can be obtained through the equation written below

$$I_{bm(i,j)}^{wm} = \gamma_{bm} * I_{bm(i,j)}^h + \beta_{bm} * I_m^w \quad (3.3)$$

Where

$I_{bm(i,j)}^{wm}$ is watermarked biometric image, (i,j) is subscript of biometric image

γ_{bm} is Scaling factor for biometric image, $I_{bm(i,j)}^h$ is host biometric image

β_{bm} is embedding factor for biometric image, I_m^w is Watermark or logo

Extraction of Watermark

The Extraction of biometric image from the watermarked biometric image can be obtained by subtracting the multiplication of embedding factor and DC coefficient of watermark divided by the scaling factor of the biometric image using the equation below

$$I_{bm(i,j)}^h = \frac{I_{bm(i,j)}^c - \beta_{bm} * I_c^w}{\gamma_{bm}} \quad (3.4)$$

$i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$

$j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$

Where

$I_{bm(i,j)}^h$ = host image or recovered biometric image, $I_{bm(i,j)}^c$ = Watermarked biometric image

β_{bm} = Embedding factor of biometric Image, I_c^w = Dc co-efficient of watermark image or logo, γ = Scaling factors of the biometric image.

[n m] = dimension of biometric image.

Fingerprint Image Extraction and Matching

The fingerprint Image enhancement that was performed in the Watermarking Scheme for Ownership Identification are Binarization, Histogram Equalization and Noise removal. Input fingerprint image was also enhanced through thinning. Following fingerprint Image enhancement is extraction of distinct features from Fingerprint image. Chouhan and Khanna (2011) revealed that feature extraction can be achieved through Crossing Number. Crossing Number is half sum of differences between pair of adjacent pixel. The ridge was denoted as ridge ending, when CN = 1 and if Crossing Number (CN) = 3, then ridge is bifurcation. This was achieved by scanning local neighborhood of each ridge pixel in fingerprint image using a 3×3 window.

Extraction of ridge features (Ridge ending and Bifurcation) was performed through pattern recognition Algorithm.

The extracted pixel value for ridge ending and ridge bifurcation was matched with captured pixel value. The distinct features of template fingerprint Image was matched with distinct feature of input fingerprint Image. The matching of fingerprint distinct feature (ridge ending and Bifurcation) involves comparing of pixel value for ridge ending and ridge bifurcation of template and Input fingerprint. The decision is matched if the pixel values are the same and decision is non-matched, if pixel values are different.

Description of proposed Architecture of Watermarking and Cryptography Biometric Model.

The proposed architecture involves acquisition of image and identification as described in figure 3. The Watermarking model initially started with capturing of fingerprint images. The acquired images will be preprocessed through Thinning, Binarization and Noise removal. The acquired and processed image was later watermarked. The watermarking was done through Discrete Cosine Transform.

Figure 1: Proposed Architecture of Watermarking scheme for ownership fingerprint identification

The identification phase involves reading of captured and Input fingerprint image. Minutiae extraction of the acquired fingerprint during identification phase was later done. The extracted distinct features can be later matched for authentication during life check.

IMPLEMENTATION OF WATERMARKING SCHEME FOR OWNERSHIP BIOMETRIC TRAIT IDENTIFICATION.

Watermarking scheme to differentiate fingerprint was implemented to make it a workable model. The model was implemented using **MATLAB** programming language as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Graphical User Interface for the watermarking technique was achieved in **MATLAB**.

Graphical User Interface to Show Watermarking of Biometric Image

Figure 2: Watermarking of sample biometric image (Fingerprint)

Model Integration and Implementation of Watermarking Scheme for Ownership Biometric Trait Identification

Figure 3: Graphical User Interface for Watermarking Fingerprint Biometric Model (Result from the same fingerprint)

Figure 4: Watermarking and Unmarking of Ear Images

Figure 5: Watermarking and Unmarking of Face Images

Performance Evaluation

Table 4.2 represents Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Mean Square Error (MSE) of watermarked Ear Image. The lowest value of Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) of watermarked ear image is 34.1463 decibel approximately 34 decibel while the greatest value of Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) of watermarked ear image is 37.8035 decibels approximately 38 decibel. The difference of the highest value and the lower value is 3.6572 decibels approximately 4 decibels.

Table 4.1: Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Mean Square Error (MSE) of Watermarked Ear Image

S/N	Ear Image Filename.bmp	PSNR in Decibel(db)	MSE
1	01-1.bmp	37.5874	11.4219
2	02-1.bmp	35.2784	19.4374
3	03-1.bmp	37.0408	12.9540
4	04-1.bmp	36.9047	13.3663
5	05-1.bmp	37.4955	11.6663
6	06-1.bmp	37.8036	10.8673
7	07-1.bmp	34.3647	23.9891
8	08-1.bmp	34.1463	25.2259
9	09-1.bmp	35.1314	20.1068
10	10-1.bmp	35.0649	20.4170

Discussion of Fingerprint Image Watermarking and Cryptography Result

As shown in Table 4.3 below, the greatest value of Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) for watermarked fingerprint images is 30.8265 decibels while the least value of Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) of watermarked fingerprint image is 30.2842 decibel. The difference of the highest value and the lowest value is 0.5423 decibels.

Table 4.2: Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Mean Square Error (MSE) of Watermarked Fingerprint Image

S/N	Fingerprint Image Filename.tiff	PSNR in Decibel(db)	MSE
1	101_1.tiff	30.2842	61.3853
2	103_1.tiff	30.7943	54.5826
3	103_3.tiff	30.4293	59.3675
4	104_2.tiff	30.8262	54.1825
5	104_3.tiff	30.8263	54.1811
6	102_2.tiff	30.8264	54.1803
7	101_3.tiff	30.8265	60.4851
8	103_1.tiff	30.4288	54.1815
9	102_3.tiff	30.7943	55.3745
10	103_2.tiff	30.7542	54.1713

Experimental Result from Face Image

Table 4.5 represents Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Mean Square Error (MSE) of watermarked face images. The highest value of Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) in decibel for facial image 26.9505 decibels.

Table 4.4: PSNR and MSE of Watermarked Face Image

S/N	Face Image (Filename.gif)	PSNR	MSE
1	Subject01.gif	23.4773	294.2697
2	Subject02.gif	23.1019	320.8420
3	Subject03.gif	23.4989	292.8117
4	Subject04.gif	23.5266	290.9503
5	Subject05.gif	23.0751	322.8266
6	Subject06.gif	26.9505	132.2605
7	Subject07.gif	24.1417	253.1124
8	Subject08.gif	23.9175	265.9081
9	Subject09.gif	23.6558	282.4261
10	Subject10.gif	23.9791	262.1596

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper presents the research conclusion and also puts forward recommendations based on this research study. Watermarking Scheme for Ownership Biometric Trait Identification has been encouraged for labeling and differentiation of current Biometric trait for Information Systems like electronic voting system that involves use of biometric images. This is crucial for copyright and ownership identification. At the end of this study, a more secured approach to biometric system was achieved through watermarking. Other security measure (Steganography) that can be demonstrated is ability to prevent intruders to easily perceive biometric images whose platform can be changed to text.

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